

ACTIVITIES OF CLUB INSTITUTIONS IN THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE 20S AND 30S OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract. This article describes the activity of club institutions established in the southern regions of Uzbekistan in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century. Types of clubs, such as workers' clubs, collective farms, women's clubs, and discussion clubs, as well as the tasks assigned to them by the Soviet state, are given.

Key words: Cultural and educational institutions, Cultural Revolution, Bolshevik Party, debate clubs, collective farm clubs, women's clubs.

Another type of cultural and educational institutions that promote the policy of the former Soviet state are clubs, and special importance was attached to the organization of their work. Club institutions play an important role in the social and cultural life of people in the society, they unite people based on certain ideas and ideologies according to the goals of their tasks, carry out public policy promotion work among the population, and improve the literacy level of people of different ages and strata. has served for the development of the way of thinking. These institutions operated on the basis of work plans drawn up according to the instructions and guidelines developed by the Bolshevik Party.

A special document on "Club work" was developed at the 2nd session of the Communist Party of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Bolsheviks) in 1925, in which there was talk of politicalizing the activities of clubs within cultural and educational institutions. In the later period, clubs were organized in such directions as party clubs, workers' clubs, Komsomol clubs, discussion clubs, collective farm clubs.

During the “Attack” movement, many women's clubs were also established in order to attract local women to club institutions [1:160].

In 1921-1924, there were 7 central club institutions in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, two of which were in the cities of Karshi and Termiz. and people from different categories were attracted to them. Party clubs carried out their activities among party members and candidates for membership, Komsomol members, leading employees. Their main task was to implement the policy of the Soviet state, organize the party community, and increase the number of party members.

In 1925, party clubs were also established in the cities of Karshi and Termiz. Since these years, the number of club institutions has increased in the southern regions of Uzbekistan. This year, 10 clubs operated in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions. [3:204] Libraries were also established under the clubs. Most of the books in them were books related to the political sphere. There are 568 books in the library of the club in the city of Karshi, of which 248 are in Russian and 320 are in Uzbek [4:39]. Clubs also have editions of “Yangi Yol”, “Red Uzbekistan”, “Mushtum”, “Fergana”, “Zarafshan” newspapers and “Mashrab” magazines and people were encouraged to support the policies of the Soviet government.

In 1927, the number of clubs in Kashkadarya region was 9. They worked in Karshi, Shahrisabz, Guzor, Yakkabog, Kitab, Koson districts of the region. In the above years, new club institutions were established in Boysun, Pattakesar, Zharkurgan, Denov, Sherabad districts of Surkhandarya region, and the number of clubs reached 14. 2 of them were women's clubs and 2 were military clubs. [5:148] In 1928, the number of clubs in Kashkadarya region was 13, and in 1929-1930 there were 17, of which 11 were working in villages.

It is known that the working class of the former Soviet state was the leading class, and the Soviet government, relying on this class, implemented its policies based on their interests. In its policy, the party paid serious attention to the ideological re-education of the working class and established clubs for them. He

received important documents related to the strengthening of his activities. Since 1924, the Soviet state exempted labor clubs from paying taxes, which gave them the opportunity to organize their activities more widely. Over the years, the number of workers' clubs has increased.

Also, in the resolution of the XIV session (December 1925) on the "Cultural work of unions", the activities of the workers' club were more widely discussed. "While developing the union's cultural work in every way, they should remember that workers' clubs and "red corners" form the basis of their activities." [6:455] The following tasks were set before the workers' clubs: to educate; attract active participation in the work of party, Komsomol, trade union organizations; promoting the fight against religion among club members; active participation in club activities; regular attendance at general meetings, trade union meetings, performances, concerts, rallies and other parties; paying membership fees on time.

In 1927-1928, there were 244 working clubs in Uzbekistan, and the number of club members was 37,632. Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions have long been considered regions with developed agriculture. The lack of industrial enterprises in these regions limited the possibility of opening labor clubs. This year, only one worker's club operated in the cities of Karshi and Termiz from the southern regions of Uzbekistan. Initially, only factory workers were involved in workers' clubs.

After the establishment of collective farms by implementing the policy of collectivization of the Soviet government, collective farm clubs were established under them. In the collective farm clubs, activities such as calling the population to collectivize, actively participating in its work, and raising the literacy of the villagers were widely promoted. In many cases, collective farm clubs organized their activities in the fields. He started giving lectures, organizing discussions, and publishing wall newspapers among the collective farmers.

In 1933, on the initiative of collective farm clubs in Denov district of Surkhondarya region, wall newspapers were published in 35 collective farms. [7:20]

In them, facts and figures related to the end of illiteracy, and information on mastering lessons were given.

In 1940, there were 2,804 club establishments in Uzbekistan. 386 of them were located in cities, 2418 in villages. In particular, there were 148 club institutions in Kashkadarya region and 86 in Surkhandarya region.

Thus, in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, the Soviet state attached special importance to the establishment of clubs, which are another type of cultural and educational institutions. Depending on the goals set by the Soviet authorities, changes were made in the activities of these institutions.

Literature.

1. Nishonboyeva Q.V. O‘zbekistonda xotin-qizlar masalasini hal etishning madaniy jihatlari (20-30 yillar): tajriba va oqibatlari. PhD diss. in historical science. – T., 1994. – P. 160.
2. Central State Archive Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan, fund 94, list 1, case 52, sheet 13.
3. Очерки истории Кашкадарьинской и Сурхандарьинской областей Узбекистана. – Т., 1968. – P. 204.
4. Kashkadarya branch of the archive of the Office of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, fund 34, list 1, case 334, sheet 39.
5. Surkhandarya Regional State Archive, fund 89, list 1, case 7, sheet 148.
6. КПСС в резолюциях и решениях съездов, конференций и пленумов ЦК (1896-1986) Т.3. Изд. док. и испр. – М., 1984. – P. 455.
7. Nurmammedova M. O‘zbekistonda madaniy-ma’rifiy ishlar. – T., 1993. – P. 20.
8. Turayeva, M. (2022). TOLERANCE ON THE EXAMPLE OF NATIONAL AND CULTURAL CENTERS IN UZBEKISTAN. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 2(06), 6-11.
9. Matluba, T. (2021). HISTORY OF ORIGIN OF THE UZBEK TERM. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(9), 71-76.

10. Тураева, М. (2017). КУЛЬТУРНАЯ ЖИЗНЬ В 20-40-Х ГОДАХ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов*, (4), 22-23.

11. Тураева, М. Х. (2017). Театральное искусство 20-х веков. *Евразийский научный журнал*, (5), 254-255.

12. Mustafayeva, M. B. (2023). MODAL SEMANTIKA TIPOLOGIYASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(2), 338-342.

13. Mustafayeva, M. B. (2021). Comparative analysis of educational terms in English and Uzbek languages. In *Experientia est optima magistra* (pp. 262-265).